

Wheat bran modified with citric acid and its application in the adsorption of methylene blue from aqueous solution

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Abstract : Wheat bran was modified with citric acid and utilized as a low cost adsorbent to remove methylene blue, a cationic dye from aqueous solutions. Batch experiments were carried out to study the effect of various experimental parameters such as initial solution pH, contact time, initial dye concentration and adsorbent dosage on methylene blue adsorption, and the optimal condition was selected. Kinetics studies showed that methylene blue adsorption process obeyed pseudo-second order rate equation. The applicability of the Langmuir and Freundlich models for the data was tested. Both the models adequately describe the experimental data of the adsorption of methylene blue. The maximum adsorption capacity calculated from the Langmuir model is 25.6 mg/g for methylene blue. The study has shown the effectiveness of modified wheat bran in the removal of methylene blue from aqueous solutions.

Keywords : Wheat bran, modification, citric acid, methylene blue, adsorption.

Introduction

Within the ecosystem, colored wastewater released in textile effluents is a dramatic source of pollution, eutrophication and perturbations in aquatic life. Chemical oxidation, chemical coagulation, biological treatment and photodegradation are some of the most commonly practiced processes for the removal of dyes from industrial wastewater. However, these methods have some disadvantages such as high reagent and energy requirements, generation of toxic sludge or other waste products that require disposal or treatment. In addition, various dyes used in the industry are particularly difficult to remove by conventional methods as they are stable to light and oxidizing agents and resistant to aerobic digestion^{1,2}. There is thus a need to search for new process that could remove dyes that are commonly used in the industry. The adsorption technique is one of the preferred methods for removal of dyes because of its efficiency and low cost. Activated carbon is the most popular and widely used adsorbent but it is expensive and its cost increase with the quality. In addition its regeneration with refractory technique results in a 10–15% loss of the adsorbent and its uptake capacity. Thus, the adsorption method uses inexpensive adsorbents as an economically feasible alterna-

tive for dye removal due to its efficiency and low operational costs. For this purpose in recent years, various biological and industrial by-products have been investigated intensively for their ability to remove dyes from aqueous solution as they can be obtained readily and are in great abundance, such as chitosan^{3,4}, waste coir pith^{5,6}, giant duckweed⁷, peanut hull^{8,9}, clays^{10,11}, fly ash^{12–14}, beer brewery waste¹⁵, bentonite¹⁶, rice bran¹⁷, rice hull¹⁸, rice husk^{19,20}, corncob²¹, eggshell²², tree's leaves²³ and wheat bran²⁴ have the potential of being used as alternative adsorbent for the removal of dyes from aqueous solutions. Among these materials, some biosorbents showed extraordinary properties for dye removal. Nevertheless, biosorbents display low adsorption selectivity and capacity toward some dye molecules. Adsorption capacity and selectivity for specific environmental pollutants can be tailored by modifying the pore structure and surface chemical properties of adsorbents²⁵. So, modifications of biosorbents through chemical functionalization can enhance its affinity for certain contaminants.

The bran of wheat is the shell of the wheat seed and contains most nutrients of wheat. This bran is usually removed in the processing of wheat into flour. It is environmentally friendly and is nutritious to the plants. There-

fore the use of wheat bran to eliminate pollution from water and wastewater is interesting. There are a few reports of heavy metal adsorption by wheat bran, as a by-product of a flour factory, such as Cr^{VI} 26, Pb^{II} 27, Cu^{II} and Cd^{II} 28. This adsorbent was effective and had high capacity for heavy metal adsorption. So the purpose of the present study was, (a) to investigate the adsorption of the cationic dye methylene blue (MB), the representative substance of dye compounds, on citric acid modified wheat bran, (b) to study the effect of different parameters such as contact time, initial pH, adsorbent dosage and initial MB concentration on adsorption process, (c) to find optimum adsorption isotherm as well as the rate of adsorption kinetics.

Experimental

Preparation of adsorbent :

The wheat bran used in this study is a by-product of a flour factory in Shenyang, China. The wheat bran was washed thoroughly with water to ensure the removal of dust and ash. It was then sieved to ~50 mesh size by passing the milled material through standard steel sieves to remove any large non-wheat bran solids. Then, about 4.0 g grinded wheat bran was mixed with 30 mL of 1.2 mol/L citric acid. The mixture was stirred until homogeneous and dried at 50 °C for 24 h. The modified wheat bran was subsequently washed with distilled water until neutral and dried at 50 °C for 24 h¹⁸. The composition of wheat bran was shown in Table 1. Moisture content was determined by drying a sample for 6 h at 110 °C. Protein content was determined by the method of Kjeldahl²⁹. Carbohydrate (glucide) was determined by Anthrone method³⁰. Dietary fiber was determined by AOAC method³¹. Lipids were extracted by the Bligh and Dyer method³². The total lipid was determined by drying an

aliquot of chloroform extract in a vacuum oven overnight weighing the resulting lipid residue. The specific surface area of sample was evaluated from nitrogen adsorption-desorption at 77 K using the Brunauer-Emmett-Teller (BET) method with a Micromeritics 2000 instrument (ASAP 2000, Micromeritics, USA). The morphology of modified wheat bran was determined by scanning electron microscopy (SEM, Philips XL-30). Infrared spectra were obtained to characterize the principal groups.

Batch adsorption experiments :

Batch technique was used to investigate MB adsorption, which was examined via kinetic studies and adsorption isotherms, together with the effect of some operating parameters. All the batch experiments were carried out in duplicate and the results given are the means with a relative standard deviation of less than 5%. Control experiments without sorbent was carried out to ascertain that the sorption was by the adsorbent and not the wall of the container.

The adsorption capacity of modified wheat bran was determined by batch adsorption isotherms at 20 °C in aqueous solution (initial pH values fixed at 3, 5 and 7). In several glass vials, 100 mL of solution containing various MB concentrations (50, 100, 150, 200, 250 mg/L) were contacted with 0.5 g of modified wheat bran. The vials were placed in a water bath at 20 °C and shaken at 150 rpm for approximately 8 h to attain an equilibrium, and the pH was maintained constant (± 0.10) adjusted either with dilute 0.1 mol/L HNO₃ or NaOH throughout the adsorption tests. The reaction mixture was then centrifuged at 3000 rpm, the MB concentrations of the various filtered solutions were analyzed by measuring the absorbency at the maximum wavelength 664 nm using a spectrophotometer (VIS-7220, Beijing, China). The amount of MB adsorbed was calculated from the following equation :

$$q_e = V(c_0 - c_e)/W \quad (1)$$

where q_e is the amount adsorbed (mg/g); c_0 and c_e are the initial and equilibrium MB concentrations in the solution (mg/L), respectively; V is the solution volume (L); and W is the mass of modified wheat bran (g).

The adsorption kinetic study was performed for MB in solution at pH 7.0 and room temperature (20 ± 1 °C). Several glass vials were used to hold 100 mL MB solu-

Table 1. Various parameters for the characterization of adsorbent

Parameters	Values
Water (Weight %)	9.9
Protein (Weight %)	15.8
Carbohydrate (Weight %)	27.3
Fiber (Weight %)	35.3
Lipid (Weight %)	3.6
Ash (Weight %)	8.1
Surface area (m ² /g)	258.2

tion of known initial concentration (50, 100 and 200 mg/L) and 0.5 g adsorbent at pH 7.0, and shaken at 150 rpm for a duration ranging from 0 to 360 min. At certain period of time, each vial was removed from the shaker, and the solution was then centrifuged at 3000 rpm to measure the MB concentration.

To determine the effects of different parameters on MB adsorption, experiments were performed at various initial pH values ranging from 3 to 10, the solution pH was maintained constant adjusted either with dilute 0.1 mol/L HNO₃ or NaOH throughout the adsorption tests. Initial concentrations of 100 mg/L MB and 0.5 g adsorbent per 100 mL of solution were employed. The suspensions were shaken at 150 rpm for 1 h. Then optimum initial pH was identified. The effects of initial dye concentration, contact time, adsorbent dosage were conducted.

Results and discussion

Characterization of modified wheat bran :

Fig. 1 shows the SEM image of the modified wheat bran. It clearly indicated the surface texture and different levels of porosity of the material. The specific surface area of the adsorbent calculated by the BET method is 258.2 m²/g.

Fig. 1. SEM image of modified wheat bran.

The FTIR spectra of the modified wheat bran before and after the adsorption of MB were shown in Fig. 2. It could be seen that the IR spectra showed five intense bands, around 3400, 2930 1700, 1450 and 1030 cm⁻¹. The broad band around 3400 cm⁻¹ was attributed to the surface hydroxyl groups and chemisorbed water. The bands at 2930 and 1700–1650 cm⁻¹ were assigned to C–H stretches of methylene groups on the surface and to ketonic and aldehydic C=O stretching frequencies, and

Fig. 2. FTIR spectra of the modified wheat brans : (a) before adsorption of MB and (b) after adsorption of MB.

to amino groups, respectively. Small peaks observed at 1465–1400 cm⁻¹ are attributed to carboxylate groups. At around 1030 cm⁻¹ the band can be assigned to phosphate and silicate groups. Therefore, the FTIR spectra of the modified wheat bran indicated the presence of ionisable functional groups able to bind with MB, and showed the influence of pH on the deprotonation of functional groups. After the adsorption of MB, the intensity of peaks became weak.

Effect of citric acid modification on adsorption process :

The comparison result on the uptake of MB by unmodified and modified wheat bran showed that the removal rate of MB is 56.36% and 87.35%, respectively. It can be seen that the adsorption of MB was enhanced when modified wheat bran was used as the adsorbent. The adsorption capacity of modified wheat bran is about 1.6 times higher than that of unmodified wheat bran, and it has higher removal efficiency for basic dye than some other biosorbents^{18,33}. The presence of carboxyl groups in modified wheat bran is believed to be primarily responsible for the adsorption of MB. Previous investigations have also postulated that the adsorption of positively charged species is due to the presence of binding sites such as carboxyl and hydroxyl groups on the surface^{26,34,35}.

Effect of initial MB concentration :

Initial concentration is one of the effective factors on

adsorption efficiency. The effect of initial MB concentrations (50, 75, 100, 150 and 200 mg/L) on percentage adsorption of MB was shown in Fig. 3. It can be seen that the MB removal rate decreased with the increase in initial

Fig. 3. Effect of initial MB concentration on the adsorption of MB (Experiment conditions employed : adsorbent dosage 5.0 g/L, solution pH 7.0, adsorption time 1 h, agitation speed 150 r/min).

MB concentration, the percentage adsorption of MB on modified wheat bran decreased from 98.8 to 43.7% as the initial MB concentration was increased from 50 to 200 mg/L. At lower MB concentrations, the ratio of the available adsorption sites of adsorbent to the initial number of molecules of MB is large and subsequently the fractional adsorption becomes independent of initial concentration. However, at higher concentrations, the available sites of adsorption become fewer, and hence the percentage removal of MB which depends upon the initial concentration, decreases³⁶.

Effect of adsorbent dosage :

The effect of adsorbent dosage on percentage adsorption of MB was shown in Fig. 4. The increase in adsorbent dosage from 1.0 to 5.0 g/L resulted in an increase from 25.8 to 89.7% in adsorption of MB. This may be due to the availability of more and more adsorption sites (carboxyl groups) for MB adsorption during the adsorption reaction. A further increase in adsorbent dosage (> 5 g/L) did not cause significant improvement in MB adsorption. This may be due to the adsorption of almost all

Fig. 4. Effect of adsorbent dosage on the adsorption of MB (Experiment conditions employed : initial MB concentration 100 mg/L, solution pH 7.0, adsorption time 1 h, agitation speed 150 r/min).

MB to the adsorbent and the establishment of equilibrium between the MB molecules adsorbed to the adsorbent and those remaining unadsorbed in the solution³⁷. Thus 5.0 g/L of modified wheat bran was chosen for next study.

Effect of initial solution pH :

The pH of the aqueous solution is an important controlling parameter in the adsorption process. The experimental results obtained from MB adsorption onto modified wheat bran under different initial pH conditions (pH = 3 ~ 10) were shown in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5. Effect of pH on the adsorption of MB (Experiment conditions employed : initial MB concentration 100 mg/L, adsorbent dosage 5.0 g/L, adsorption time 1 h, agitation speed 150 r/min).

It is evident that the percentage of MB removal strongly depended on the solution pH. The removal of MB increased dramatically with increasing pH at pH = 3~5, when the solution pH = 6~10, the increases slowly with increasing pH. This is an agreement with the observations of previous reports on the adsorption of MB¹⁸. At low pH, the removal of MB was suppressed by H⁺ ions that surrounded the surface of the adsorbent hindering the approach of MB to the carboxylate groups present on the surface of modified wheat bran. The protonation of carboxylate groups would also reduce the MB adsorption. With increasing pH, adsorption of MB became favorable due to the deprotonation of carboxyl groups, resulting in more adsorption sites available for binding with MB. This phenomenon favors the adsorption of positively charged dye due to electrostatic attraction⁵. Therefore, the pH 7.0 was chosen for the following experiments.

Effect of contact time :

Contact time is one of the effective factors in batch adsorption process. The effect of contact time on MB adsorption efficiency was shown in Fig. 6. As it is shown, the adsorption was very fast and equilibrium between the

Fig. 6. Effect of contact time on the adsorption of MB (Experiment conditions employed : initial MB concentration 100 mg/L, adsorbent dosage 5.0 g/L, solution pH 7.0, agitation speed 150 r/min).

aqueous solution and modified wheat bran was established within about 1 h. There was no significant change in MB removal rates after 1 h up to 3 h. Based on these results,

1 h was taken as the equilibrium time in adsorption experiments. The removal of MB from aqueous solutions by adsorption on modified wheat bran increases with contact time, till the equilibrium is attained. Similar results have been reported in literature for removal of dyes^{38,39}.

Adsorption isotherms :

The adsorption isotherm of MB obtained for modified wheat bran was shown in Fig. 7. These isotherms represent the adsorption behavior of MB on the adsorbent as a function of increasing aqueous MB concentration for a contact time of 8 h. The isotherm showed that the adsorption capacity increased with increasing equilibrium concentration of MB.

Fig. 7. Adsorption isotherms for MB by modified wheat bran (Experimental conditions employed : adsorbent dosage 5.0 g/L, adsorption time 8 h, agitation speed 150 r/min).

The results of MB adsorption on modified wheat bran (Fig. 7) were analyzed using Langmuir model to evaluate parameters associated to the adsorption behavior. The linear form of Langmuir equation at a given temperature is represented by :

$$q_e = q_m \cdot b \cdot c_e / (1 + b \cdot c_e) \tag{2}$$

where c_e is the aqueous phase MB equilibrium concentration (mg/L), q_e is the amount of MB sorbet onto 1 g of the considered adsorbent (mg/g), b is the adsorption constant (L/mg) related to the energy of adsorption and represents the affinity between the adsorbent and adsorbate, q_m is the maximum adsorption capacity (mg/g).

Eq. (2) can be rearranged to obtain :

$$c_e/q_e = 1/(b \cdot q_m) + c_e/q_m \quad (3)$$

The adsorption data fit to the linear form of the Langmuir equation can be obtained by plotting of c_e/q_e against c_e . This linear plot was employed to obtain the values of q_m and b (Table 2) from the slope and intercept of the plot. It could be seen that both q_m and b increased with increasing initial pH from 3.0 to 7.0. The maxima adsorption capacities (q_m) were 16.483, 21.864 and 25.092 mg/g at pH values 3, 5 and 7, respectively. High values of b were reflected in the steep initial slope of an adsorption isotherm, indicating desirable high affinity⁴⁰. Therefore, modified wheat bran performed well in MB adsorption at initial pH 7.0 compared to other initial pH values examined.

Initial pH	Langmuir equation			Freundlich equation		
	q_m (mg g ⁻¹)	b (L mg ⁻¹)	R^2	$1/n$	K_f	R^2
3.0	16.483	0.1809	0.9997	0.1808	5.6863	0.9602
5.0	21.864	0.3172	0.9998	0.1506	7.3161	0.9806
7.0	25.092	0.6634	0.9994	0.1098	11.6268	0.9993

The Freundlich isotherm model was also used to analyze the results of MB adsorption on modified wheat bran (Fig. 7). The Freundlich model can be expressed by the following equation :

$$q_e = k_f \cdot c_e^{1/n} \quad (4)$$

where k_f and n are constants related to the adsorption capacity and affinity, respectively. The equation is conveniently used in the linear form by taking the logarithm of both sides as :

$$\lg q_e = \lg k_f + (1/n) \lg c_e \quad (5)$$

The adsorption data fit to the linear form of the Freundlich equation can be obtained by plotting of $\lg q_e$ against $\lg c_e$. The Freundlich isotherm parameters obtained for the adsorption of MB on modified wheat bran were listed in Table 2. The data showed that the k_f constant was increased with the increase of initial pH values, at initial pH 7.0, k_f reached its corresponding maximum value, and $1/n$ value at initial pH 7.0 was smaller than that at other initial pH values. These implied that the affinity between the adsorbent and MB molecules was also higher

than other initial pH values⁴². From Table 2, the Langmuir adsorption isotherm yielded better fit as indicated by the higher R^2 values at all pH values compared to the Freundlich adsorption isotherm model.

Kinetic study :

In order to obtain the adsorption kinetic information of MB on the modified wheat bran adsorbent, the change of MB concentration with adsorption time was shown in Fig. 8. It could be seen that the adsorption of MB increased rapidly with time as well as with the increase of the initial MB concentrations. However, the time to reach

Fig. 8. Adsorption kinetics of MB by modified wheat bran (Experimental conditions employed : pH 7.0, agitation speed 150 r/min, adsorbent dosage 5.0 g/L).

the adsorption equilibrium took longer with an increase in the concentration. The adsorption of MB reached to equilibrium state after 30 min reaction at initial MB concentration of 50 mg/L. For the initial MB concentration of 200 mg/L, the adsorption time reached to equilibrium state was more than 120 min.

To investigate the mechanism of adsorption, the pseudo-second order kinetic model was applied to experimental data. The pseudo-second order kinetic equation could be derived as⁴¹ :

$$dq_t/dt = k_2(q_e - q_t)^2 \quad (6)$$

The pseudo-second order kinetic equation is conveniently used in the linear form as :

$$t/q_t = 1/(k_2 \cdot q_e^2) + t/q_e \quad (7)$$

The kinetic experimental data of MB on the modified

wheat bran fit to the linear form of the pseudo-second order kinetic equation can be obtained by plotting of t/q_t against t . This linear plot was employed to obtain the kinetic constant, k_2 and q_e from the intercept and slope of the plot. The results were listed in Table 3. Remarkably, the kinetic data could be described well by the pseudo-second order rate equation which was based on the assumption that the rate limiting step may be chemical sorption or chemisorptions involving valency forces through sharing or exchange of electron between adsorbent and adsorbate⁴². It could also be seen that the values of the pseudo-second order rate constant decreased with increasing the initial MB concentrations. This result was accordant with previous report¹⁸.

Table 3. Kinetic parameters for MB adsorption by modified wheat bran

C_0 (mg L ⁻¹)	q_e (mg g ⁻¹)	k_2 (L mg ⁻¹ min ⁻¹)	R^2
50	10.084	2.146×10^{-2}	0.9998
100	18.272	3.473×10^{-3}	0.9994
200	20.816	2.024×10^{-3}	0.9996

Treatment of real wastewater samples :

The prepared biosorbent (citric acid modified wheat bran) was used to treat a variety of real wastewater samples (information for the characterization listed in Table 4) to evaluate the applicability of the adsorbent. The experiments were carried out with constant temperature (20 °C), pH (7.0), contact time (1 h) and adsorbent dosage

Table 4. Treatment results of real dye wastewater with citric acid modified wheat bran

Sample	pH	COD (mg/L)	BOD (mg/L)	SS (mg/L)	$C_{0,MB}$ (mg/L)	Removal rate of MB (%)
1	6.8	190.9	72.7	56.6	36.16	97.57
2	7.2	273.6	98.2	69.5	65.49	93.95
3	8.0	382.7	103.4	98.3	90.26	90.51
4	9.2	400.6	150.8	122.6	101.85	86.3
5	8.8	423.9	166.1	114.7	112.65	80.12

(7.0 g/L). The MB concentrations of real wastewater samples were analyzed by measuring the absorbency at the maximum wavelength 664 nm using a spectrophotometer. The experimental results were listed in Table 4. It was observed that MB could be removed efficiently by the citric acid modified wheat bran adsorbent. The MB

removal percentages of real wastewater samples were higher than 80%. Thus it is suggested that the applicability of the prepared adsorbent in wastewater treatment containing dye was satisfactory. Therefore, it is potentially employable for polluted water treatment processes.

Conclusions

Citric acid modified wheat bran was utilized as adsorbent to remove methyl blue (MB), a basic dye from aqueous solution by adsorption. The modification of wheat bran by citric acid significantly improved its adsorption capacity, the adsorption capacity of modified wheat bran for MB is about 1.6 times higher than that of unmodified wheat bran, its equilibrium adsorption capacity is 25.1 mg/g for MB, and made this material a suitable adsorbent to remove MB from synthetic solutions. The amount of MB adsorbed was found to vary with initial solution pH and contact time. The overall adsorption rate was illustrated by the pseudo-second order kinetic model. The equilibrium data obtained from this study was well presented by Langmuir model. As wheat bran is readily available in great abundance in China, it can be considered as an attractive alternative to the more expensive technologies used in wastewater treatment containing dye.

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